

Coleoptera, Archostemata

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Radio-medial bridges in Archostemata

Cupedidae: *Priaema serrata*

- a) wing extended, dorsal view
- b) wing extended, ventral view
- c) hind wing closed

Ommatididae: *Tetraphalerus*

CuP, claval line, AA 1+2 reduced

Cupedidae: *Disticupes*

Cupedidae: *Disticipes varians*

Cupedidae: *Disticipes varians*

Cupedidae: *Disticipes* sp.

13mm

Cupedidae

HIND WING

Priacma serrata

Coleoptera: Archostemata: *Priacma serrata* (Cupedidae)

Coleoptera apomorphies in hind wing articulation:
 AX-PC & C (tegula) reduced; B-R partly membranized; F-M subdivided; B-M large, connected with B-Cu; AX-Cu (3Ax) small, sutured, and often fragmented; AX-Cu fused with F-Cu; F-Cu fused with FA

Cupedidae: *Priacma serrata*

PI esiomorphy: ScP not fused to RA; RP 1+2 reduced

11 mm

Micromalthidae: *Micromalthus debilis*

CuA very clearly fuses to MP 3+4 branch (in many Coleoptera this fusion is not so clearly expressed)

Lmm

HW Ommatidae: *Omma stanleyi*

Articular sclerites: old nomenclature

Ommatidae: *Omma stanleyi*

Apomorphies: both medial fulcalare (F-M) and medial basivene (B-M) are subdivided!
 F-A replaced by a link

Ommatidae: *Omma stanleyi*

Note that CuA sends out branch CuA 3+4 to serve as a supporting strut
 CuP and claval line reduced

Ommatidae: *Omma stanleyi*

Note that RA 3+4 forms only the bottom of the radial cell

Ommatidae: Omma

Ommatidae: *Tetraphalerus wagneri*

Important plesiomorphy: RA distinctly and broadly forks and encloses radial cell